

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE BATTLE OF MONTE CASSINO: DISPUTES AND CONSENTS WITHIN ANDERS' ARMY

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Abstract

The article reveals the participation of the Second Polish Army Corps led by general Anders in the battle of Monte Cassino. The author highlights how the discussions within Polish military commanders affected the planning of Monte Cassino battle and its outcome. The memoirs of Polish generals who were in charge of military operations in Poland and abroad emphasise that even before the battle Polish commanders attached great importance to the operation at Monte Cassino as the victory in Italy could serve for strengthening the positions of Armia Krajowa in its fight against both the Germans and the Soviets.

Keywords: Second Polish Army Corps, general Anders, general Sosnkowski, Monte Cassino

The historiography of the battle at Monte Cassino has unveiled a lot of intriguing details on the plans of the military commanders, their strategies and the aftermath of the battle. However, the full story of the participation in the battle of the Second Polish Army Corps is yet to be written. This article is aimed at analyzing the development of the plans of Polish commanders that reveal how the discussions within different groups of Polish officers affected the outcome of the battle.

The Second Polish Army Corps was reorganized from the so-called Anders Army, formed on the territory of the Soviet Union in 1941-1942. Subsequently, the soldiers were evacuated to the territory of Iran, and then Palestine. In summer of 1943, the Second Polish Army Corps was created on the basis of Anders' army and included the following units: 3rd Carpathian Infantry Division; 5th Cross Infantry Division; 2nd Warsaw Armoured Brigade and 2nd Artillery Corps. In December 1943, the corps units were relocated to Italy, where they came into operational subordination of the 8th British Army. The commanders of the British Army assigned the corps to act simultaneously with the units of the 8th British Army with the following tasks to be accomplished: to cut off the highway and the valley from the south, to cut off the height from the north and north-west and break through the main German line of defence to ensure the dominance on the Naples-Rome highway. Consequently, they had to attack and occupy a monastery on the top of the mountain and finally capture the settlement of Piedimonte located on its opposite slope³.

The commander the Second Polish Army Corps general Vladislav Anders described in his memoirs how the decision on the participation of Polish troops in this battle was taken. He stated that on March 23, General Liz arrived in Vinea Touro to give the latest news. The Germans repulsed the assault on the city Cassino. The Allied forces on the Anzio bridgehead were in a difficult position, so it was decided to conduct a large offensive on the Italian front from the city of

Cassino to the coast of the Tyrrhenian Sea. The Second Polish Army Corps was entrusted with a difficult task – the capture of the abbey on Monte Cassino, and then the capture of Piedimonte. General Anders wrote that "this would bring great glory to Polish weapons. I have assessed the risk of this operation, the inevitable losses and my full responsibility in case of failure. After a brief reflection, I declared that I would fulfil this difficult task"⁴. Thus, Polish generals were aware of the scale of the offensive and their possible casualties.

However, it was later revealed that general Anders made this difficult decision without the consent of his supreme Commander-in-Chief general Kazimierz Sosnkowski who, according to his memoirs, was horrified, especially by the plan to attack a well-fortified German position directly in the forehead. War correspondent of the Second Polish Army Corps Melchior Vankovich recalled the enemy fortifications that Polish soldiers had to overcome: "it was a series of bunkers for three people each, reinforced concrete with a steel beam, with narrow loopholes for machine guns or flamethrowers. These bunkers were located on a triangle, so that there was a crossfire. The territory in front of the bunkers was mined and also fenced with barbed wire"⁵.

The two Polish generals had divergence in their positions on how the battle is to be planned. This divergence led to a conflict between them. Both opponents left notes about the conflict on the pages of their memoirs. General Anders limited himself to a few general phrases, reducing the dispute to tactical issues. General Sosnkovsky directly accused the commander of the Second Polish Army Corps of following his personal ambitions saying that he considers the "arbitrariness a violation of military discipline, and very dangerous and harmful in emigration". What is more, "disposing of Polish blood in the difficult political struggle for the future and rights of our people is the business of the highest authorities of the Polish Republic and that ignoring these bodies in favour of foreign political forces allows the latter to win private ambitions in the name of their

³ Armia Andersa w dokumentach. T. 3. Londyn, 1973. P. 68
⁴ Władysław Anders: Bez ostatniego rozdziału.

Wspomnienia z lat 1939–1946, Warszawa, 2017. P. 112-114

⁵ Белорусские герои Монте-Кассино. Сборник воспоминаний / под ред. Е.С. Шахорко. Минск, 2013. P. 49

own interests, which may, after all, run counter to our own national interests".⁶

These memoirs emphasise that even before the battle Polish commanders attached great importance to this operation. This can also be confirmed by the "Order before the Battle" authored by general Vladislav Anders, which dates back to May 11, 1944.⁷

During the eight days of fighting, the Second Polish Army Corps lost 1,074 people killed and 4,199 wounded, as well as up to 400 missing, which amounted to more than 10% of the number of the corps and more than a third of its losses for the entire period of hostilities of war.⁸ However, on May 19, 1944, all the goals set for the units of the Second Polish Army Corps were achieved. According to Anders' memoirs, "the 12th regiment of Podolsk lancers finally occupied the ruins of the monastery at 9:50 and hung out the Polish flag there". This was the end of the history of the Battle of Monte Cassino, but he also stated that this victory "only continued the battle for Poland".⁹

After the capture of Monte Cassino by the Allies and the breakthrough of the Gustav Line, the Germans left Rome without a fight, American troops entered the city on June 4, 1944. The Nazis began to withdraw in an organized manner to a new defensive line - the "Gothic Line", which passed to the north of the Italian capital. The Allies pursued them. The 8th British army, which included the Second Polish Army Corps, struck the main blow along the Adriatic coast, meaning then to turn from the sea (from the Rimini area) deep into the Apennines, to Bologna. In the summer of 1944 The Poles occupied the port of Ancona, then, together with other allied troops, they wedged into the "Gothic Line". However, the advance was too slow. As a result, the

Allies broke through the enemy's fortified line, but in December, when there was very little left to Bologna, their offensive froze. The task of reaching the Po River Valley in northern Italy has not been solved.

On April 21, 1945, the Allied forces entered Bologna. Poles were in the front ranks of the liberators. They were greeted with joy by the local population. Seventeen Polish officers received the title of honorary citizens of Bologna, and several Polish soldiers were later awarded medals with the inscription "Liberators who were the first to enter Bologna - April 21, 1945 - in honor of their success."

After the end of the war, General Anders' troops remained in Italy as part of the occupation forces. Most of the Polish soldiers did not want to return to Poland, which had fallen under the rule of the Communists. In 1946, they were transferred to the UK, where they remained permanently.

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⁶ Lech Wyszczelski: Generał Kazimierz Sosnkowski. – Warszawa: Bellona, 2018. P. 210-211

⁷ Władysław Anders: Bez ostatniego rozdziału.

Wspomnienia z lat 1939–1946, Warszawa, 2017. P. 118-119

⁸ Michał Polak, Logistyczne zabezpieczenie działań 2-go Korpusu Polskiego (grudzień 1944 – kwiecień 1945), Przegąd Historyczno-Wojskowy. Warszawa 2005. P. 72

⁹ Władysław Anders: Bez ostatniego rozdziału.

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